

THE POTENTIAL INHIBITION AGAINST ENZYMES TARGET TYPE 2 DIABETES'S PATHWAYS OF LEONURISIDE VIA VIRTUAL STUDIES

Ho Thi Thanh Thanh¹, Pham Thi Huyen Thoa², Nguyen Thi Tu Oanh³, Nguyen Anh Dung²,
 Nguyen Van Bon²

Received Date: 18/02/2024; Revised Date: 27/05/2024; Accepted for Publication: 01/06/2024

ABSTRACT

Leonuriside (LN) is a natural compound previously purified from *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. and was found as a novel inhibitor of enzyme-targeting type 2 diabetes (T2D) treatment in our early reports via in vitro tests. This study aims to further characterize LN as a potential inhibitor of α -glucosidase and α -amylase and its high possibility of being developed as an antidiabetic drug via in silico studies. The result of the docking study indicated that LN could bind to targeting enzymes α -glucosidase (Q6P7A9) and α -amylase (1SMD) via forming stable complexes with acceptable root mean square deviation (RMSD) values ($< 2.0\text{\AA}$) and good binding energy with low docking score (DS) values of -11.3 and -11.9 kcal/mol, respectively. The drug-likeness, and ADMET properties of LN were further investigated. The drug-likeness properties of LN were further investigated. The data of Lipinski's rule of five analysis and absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity (ADMET)-based pharmacokinetics and pharmacology revealed that LN possesses all the properties fitting the requirement of Lipkin's Rules and good ADMET properties in the required allotted limitation. The results obtained in this work suggested LN is a potential inhibitor of α -glucosidase and α -amylase and may be developed as a T2D drug.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes, Leonuriside, *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ., α -glucosidase, α -amylase, in silico.

1. INTRODUCTION

Type-2 diabetes (T2D), a chronic metabolic disorder significantly reduces people's life quality worldwide (Sato K. et al., 2019). The use of α -amylase inhibitors (aAIs) and α -glucosidase inhibitors (aGIs) has been recognized as one of the effective therapies for the management of T2D (DeMelo E.B. et al., 2006; Nguyen T.H. et al., 2022). Up till now, some commercial inhibitors such as acarbose, voglibose, and miglitol have been available for use. However, side effects were found in type 2 diabetes patients when utilizing the therapy with the above inhibitors (Nguyen V.B. et al., 2017a), as such, searching for new and natural enzyme inhibitors for T2D management still is an important task in research.

Enzyme inhibitors including aAIs and aGIs may be obtained from some major sources such as microbes, chemical synthesis, and medicinal plants (Ghani U., 2015; Nguyen V.B. et al., 2018a; Dirir A.M. et al., 2021). Among these, the extracts from medicinal plants have been considered as potential and natural sources for obtaining aAIs and aGIs (Ghani U., 2015; Dirir A.M. et al., 2021). Thus, the studies concerned with screening and identifying active inhibitors from herbal extracts

received much interest worldwide.

Euonymus laxiflorus Champ. (ELC) is a medicinal plant distributed in several Asian countries such as Vietnam, China, Myanmar, Cambodia, and India (Nguyen V.B. et al., 2018b). These herbal extracts were reported to show anti-xanthine oxidase and reduced serum uric acid levels in rats (Liu L.M. et al., 2016), antioxidant, anti-NO, prebiotic, and anticancer effects (Nguyen V.B. et al., 2018b; Nguyen Q.V. et al., 2017). In our earlier works, this herbal was also screened as a potential source of aAIs (Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2017b) and aGIs (Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2017c). Of the purified compounds from ELC, the bioactive compound LN was found as novel aAIs and aGI (Nguyen V.B. et al., 2018c; Nguyen V.B. et al., 2018d). However, the basic drug properties as well as the binding energy of this compound toward the targeting enzymes are unknown. In this study, we investigate the interaction and binding energy of LN towards targeting enzymes Q6P7A9 and α -1SMD. The drug-likeness properties of LN were also investigated via the virtual study.

2. STUDY CONTENTS, MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study contents

¹Department of Science and Technology of DakLak Province, Vietnam;

²Tay Nguyen University, Buon Ma Thuot City, Vietnam;

³Phan Boi Chau High School, Cu Jut district, Dak Nong province, Vietnam;

Corresponding author: Nguyen Van Bon; Tel: 0842458283; Email: nvbon@ttn.edu.vn.

Potential enzymes inhibitory effect of LN via docking study.

The frontier molecular orbitals of LN.

The drug-likeness and ADMET Properties LN.

2.2. Methodologies

2.2.1. Docking study protocol

Docking study was performed following several typical steps mentioned in the previous works (Nguyen T.H. et al., 2022; Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2023).

- *Preparing enzyme structures:* The data structures of enzymes Q6P7A9 and 1SMD were obtained from the Worldwide Protein Data Bank. The 3-D structures of these enzymes were prepared using MOE-2015.10 software and the binding sites on enzymes were found using the function of site finder in MOE. The pH is 7.0 for preparing enzyme structures.

- *Preparing ligand structures:* the 3D structures of ligands LN and acarbose (AC) were prepared and optimized using ChemBioOffice 2018 software and MOE software, respectively.

- *Performance and the output data of docking:* The ligands LN and AC were docked into the binding sites on enzymes Q6P7A9 and 1SMD using MOE. The docking score (DS), the root mean square deviation (RMSD), linkage types, amino acid compositions, and the linkage distances were harvested for analysis.

2.2.2. The Lipkin's Rules of Five analysis

The properties of drug-likeness of the compounds were investigated by Lipkin's Rules of Five performance using the online software which is available for access at (<http://www.scfbioitd.res.in/software/drugdesign/lipinski.jsp>).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Potential enzymes inhibitory effect of Leonuriside via docking study

When docking a ligand (inhibitor) into its targeting protein (enzyme), the ligand may interact with the enzyme at various sites on the enzyme (named binding sites, BSs). Thus, only the most stable intermolecular structure was selected for further investigation (Gligorić E. et al., 2019). Using the site finder function of MOE, the most active BSs on enzyme Q6P7A9 (Figure 1a) and 1SMD (Figure 1b). The BS on enzyme Q6P7A9 contained 59 amino acids with some residues, including Phe362, Met363, Arg594, Pro595, Arg608, His714, His717, Val718, Phe859, Asp861, Ser865, Leu866, Gly867, Val868, Leu869, and Glu870. The BS on 1SMD enzyme was also found containing 59 amino acids with some residues as below: Arg267, Asn301, Gln302, Arg303, Gly304, His305, Gly309, Ala310, Ser311,

Ile312, Thr314, Trp316, Asp317, Trp344, Arg346, Phe348, Gly351, Lys352, Asp353, and Asp356.

In the virtual study, the values of RMSD and DS have been used as important indicators for determining the successful interaction ($\text{RMSD} \leq 2.0\text{\AA}$) and effective inhibitory effect ($\text{DS} \leq -3.20\text{ kcal/mol}$) of an inhibitor towards the targeting enzyme (Ding Y. et al., 2016; Chandra B.T.M. et al., 2017).

As presented in Table 1, LN displayed significant interaction with enzymes Q6P7A9 and 1SMD with very low RMSD values of 1.53 and 1.73 Å, respectively. AC, a commercial inhibitor was also previously found interacting with these enzymes with accepted RMSD values of 0.94 and 1.59 Å, respectively (Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2023; Nguyen T.H. et al., 2022). These ligands showed efficient binding energy to enzyme Q6P7A9 and 1SMD with DS values of -11.2 to -11.3 kcal/mol and -11.9 to -12.1 kcal/mol, respectively. These results suggested LN is a potential inhibitor of Q6P7A9 and 1SMD. For an inside understanding of the interaction of LN toward targeting enzymes, the binding of this ligand with Q6P7A9 and 1SMD at the binding sites were also recorded and presented in Table 2, Figure 2, and Figure 3.

Figure 1. The 3D structures and binding sites of enzymes Q6P7A9 (a) and 1SMD (b)

Table 1. The data of docking study of ligands LN and AC binding with Q6P7A9 and 1SM

Ligand	Enzyme	RMSD (Å)	DS (kcal/mol)	Ref.
LN	Q6P7A9	1.5	-11.3	This study
AC	Q6P7A9	0.94	-11.4	[*]
LN	1SM	1.7	-11.9	This study
AC	1SM	1.59	-12.1	[**]

Referenced from the previous reports: Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2023 (*); Nguyen T.H. et al., 2022 (**).

Table 2. The data of linkages, the distance, and energy binding of the interaction between ligands LN and enzymes Q6P7A9 and 1SM

Complex	Linkages	Amino acids [Distance (Å)/E (kcal/mol)/ linkage type]
LN-Q6P7A9	6 linkages (4H-donor, 2H-acceptor)	His717(3.30/-0.7/H-donor) Glu870(2.78/-3.7/H-donor) Ser865(2.73/-2.2/H-donor) Ser584(2.89/-2.0/H-donor) Gly867(3.25/-1.6/H-acceptor) Val868(2.99/-2.3/H-acceptor)
LN-1SM	3 linkages (2H-donor, 1pi-H)	Asp317(3.00/-3.2/H-donor) Asn301(2.84/-2.2/H-donor) Phe348(3.59/-0.6/pi-H)

The ligand LN effectively bound to enzyme Q6P7A9 (Figure 2) by interacting with 6 amino acids, including His717, Glu870, Ser865, Ser584, Gly867, and Val868 for creating 6 linkages. Of these, 4 H-donor and 2 H-acceptor linkages were formed (Table 2). This ligand was also found interacting with enzyme 1SM (Figure 3) at its active zone with good binding energy via connecting with several amino acids (Asp317, Asn301, and Phe348), and 3 linkages were

generated. Of those, 2 H-donor linkages were formed via the interaction of LN with Asp317, and Asn301 while 1pi-H was created via the interaction of LN with Phe348 (Table 2). In our previous works, acarbose was also found highly bound to enzymes Q6P7A9 (Nguyen, V.B. et al., 2023) and 1SM (Nguyen T.H. et al., 2022) via creating 5 linkages (2 H-donor, 3 H-acceptor) and 4 linkages (1 H-donor and 3 H-acceptor), respectively.

Figure 2. Interaction of ligand LN with enzyme Q6P7A9 (a). The 3D (b) and 2D (c) structures of ligand LN at the active site 1 of Q6P7A9

high possibility of being used as a potential drug. commercial inhibitor only satisfied approximately
 Acarbose was analyzed for comparison and this 2 rules.

Table 3. The Lipkin's Rules of Five of LN and AC

Rules	Ligands		Lipki's rules
	LN	AC	
Mass (Da)	332	646	< 500
H-donor	5	15	< 5
H-acceptors	9	18	< 10
LogP	-1.88	-9.59	< 5
Molar Refractivity	75.6	136.5	40-130

The ADMET properties of LN and AC were explored (Table 4). Regarding the absorption property, LN played howed a high level of intestinal absorption (human) values in the range of 34.57%, while AC showed a very poor ability of absorption of 4.172 %. In terms of drug distribution, the log VDss value of LN was found at $-0.047 \log L.kg^{-1}$, indicating that this inhibitor compound showed a plasma-tissue balance ($-0.15 < \log VDss < 0.45$). AC showed a low VDss value of -0.836 , indicating Its preference for blood plasma over tissue (Sarukhanyan E. et al., 2022). Both these inhibitors (LN and AC) may not cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB) since their BBB permeability

values were low ($\log BB < -1$). Concerning metabolism, LN and ABC found no effects on the substrates and inhibitors of the cytochromes P450 family, indicating that these compounds may not be oxidized in the liver and may be stable in the living system [20]. Regarding the property of excretion, the prediction that LN and AC may be carried out via the Organic Cation Transporter 2 due to having total clearance values of 0.72 and 0.428 $\log mL.min^{-1}.kg^{-1}$, respectively [12]. Notably, both LN and AC demonstrated no AMES toxicity. Overall, LN displayed good ADMET properties in the required allotted limitation.

Table 4. The ADMET properties of LN and AC

Property	LN	AC	Unit
Absorption			
Water solubility	-2.203	-1.482	(1)
Caco2 permeability	-0.195	-0.481	(2)
Intestinal-absorption	34.57	4.172	(3)
Skin-permeability	-2.741	-2.735	(4)
P-glycoprotein substrate	Yes	Yes	(5)
P-glycoprotein I inhibitor	No	No	(5)
P-glycoprotein II inhibitor	No	No	(5)
Distribution			
VDss	-0.047	-0.836	(6)
Fraction-unbound	0.509	0.505	(6)
BBB permeability	-1.375	-1.717	(7)
CNS permeability	-4.673	-6.438	(8)
Metabolism			
CYP2D6 substrate	No	No	(5)
CYP3A4 substrate	No	No	(5)
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	(5)
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	No	(5)
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	No	(5)
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	No	(5)

Property	LN	AC	Unit
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No	(5)
Excretion			
Total Clearance	0.72	0.428	(9)
Renal OCT2 substrate	No	No	(5)
Toxicity			
AMES toxicity	No	No	(5)
Max. tolerated dose	0.402	0.435	(10)
hERG I inhibitor	No	No	(5)
hERG II inhibitor	No	Yes	(5)
Oral Rat Acute-toxicity (LD50)	2.787	2.449	(11)
Oral Rat Chronic Toxicity	4.367	5.319	(12)
Hepatotoxicity	No	No	(5)
Skin Sensitization	No	No	(5)
T.Pyriformis toxicity	0.285	0.285	(13)
Minnow-toxicity	3.719	16.823	(14)

Note: (1) $\log \text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$; (2) $\log \text{Papp}$ ($10^{-6} \text{ cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$); (3) %; (4) $\log \text{Kp}$; (5) Yes/No; (6) $\log \text{L}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; (7) $\log \text{BB}$; (8) $\log \text{PS}$; (9) $\log \text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; (10) $\log \text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$; (11) $\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; (12) $\log \text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{bw}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$; (13) $\log \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$; (14) $\log \text{mM}$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

LN was characterized as a potential antidiabetic compound via virtual studies in this study. LN was found highly binding to enzymes Q6P7A9 and α -1SMD associating with type 2 diabetes with acceptable RMSD value ($\leq 2.0\text{\AA}$) and good DS values of -11.3 and -11.9 kcal/mol, respectively. These energy binding of LN are comparable to those of acarbose, an antidiabetic compound with DS values of -11.2 to -12.7 kcal/mol, respectively. Furthermore, based on Lipkin's Rules of Five analysis, this compound demonstrated good drug-likeness properties and displayed good ADMET properties in the required allotted limitation, thus, it has a high possibility to be used as a potential

drug for the management of type 2 diabetes.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, resources, writing—original draft preparation, NVB; methodology, software and validation, data curation, visualization, and project administration, writing—review, and editing, NVB., HTTT, and PTHT; formal analysis, HTTT, NTTO, NAD, and N.V.B; investigation, HTTT, NTTO, and T.H.T.P.

FUNDING

This study was fully supported by a grant from Tay Nguyen University [Grant No. T2023-02CBTĐ].

TIỀM NĂNG ỨC CHẾ ENZYME MỤC TIÊU KHÁNG TIỂU ĐƯỜNG TYPE 2 CỦA HỢP CHẤT LEONURISIDE THÔNG QUA NGHIÊN CỨU IN SILICO

Hồ Thị Thanh Thanh¹, Phạm Thị Huyền Thoa², Nguyễn Thị Tú Oanh³, Nguyễn Anh Dũng², Nguyễn Văn Bón²

Ngày nhận bài: 18/02/2024; Ngày phản biện thông qua: 27/05/2024; Ngày duyệt đăng: 01/06/2024

TÓM TẮT

Leonuriside (LN) – một hợp chất tự nhiên đã được cô lập từ *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. và được ghi nhận mới là chất ức chế enzyme tiềm năng liên quan tới bệnh tiểu đường type 2 trong công bố trước của chúng tôi. Mục tiêu của nghiên cứu này là xác định tiềm năng ức chế và khả năng phát triển thuốc kháng tiểu đường của LN thông qua nghiên cứu mô phỏng. Kết quả mô phỏng cho thấy, LN tương tác và tạo phức bền với enzyme α -glucosidase (Q6P7A9) và α -amylase (1SMD) với giá trị RMSD được chấp nhận ($< 2.0\text{\AA}$) và năng lượng liên kết tương ứng là 11.3 and -11.9 kcal/mol. Đặc tính thuốc của hợp chất LN cũng được nghiên cứu. Kết quả phân tích 5 nguyên tắc của Lipkin và được lý dựa trên năm phân tích và hấp thụ, phân phối, chuyển hóa, bài tiết và độc tính (ADMET) của Lipinski cho thấy hoạt chất này đáp ứng đầy đủ cả 5 nguyên tắc của Lipkin và có những đặc tính tốt về dược lý. Những kết quả ghi nhận trong báo cáo này minh chứng và đề nghị hợp chất LN là chất ức chế enzyme tiềm năng và có khả năng phát triển thuốc kháng tiểu đường type 2.

Từ khóa: Tiểu đường type 2, Leonuriside, *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ., α -glucosidase, α -amylase, in silico.

REFERENCES

- Chandra B.T.M., Rajesh S.S., Bhaskar B.V., Devi S., Rammohan A., Sivaraman T., Rajendra W (2017). Molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulation, biological evaluation and 2D QSAR analysis of flavonoids from *Syzygium alternifolium* as potent anti-*Helicobacter pylori* agents. *RSC Advances*, 7:18277–18292.
- DeMelo E.B., Gomes A., Carvalha I (2006). α -and β -Glucosidase inhibitors: Chemical structure and biological activity. *J. Tetrahedr.*, 62:10277–10302.
- Ding Y., Fang Y., Moreno J., Ramanujam J., Jarrell M., Brylinski M (2016). Assessing the similarity of ligand binding conformations with the contact mode score. *Computational Biology and Chemistry*, 64:403–413.
- Dirir A.M., Daou M., Yousef A.F., Yousef L.F (2021). A review of alpha-glucosidase inhibitors from plants as potential candidates for the treatment of type-2 diabetes. *Phytochemistry Rev.*, 21(4):1049-1079.
- Ghani U (2015). Re-exploring promising α -glucosidase inhibitors for potential development into oral anti-diabetic drugs: Finding needle in the haystack. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 103:133–162.
- Gligorić E., Igić R., Suvajdžić L., Grujić-Letić N (2019). Species of the Genus *Salix*, L.: Biochemical screening and molecular docking approach to potential acetylcholinesterase inhibitors. *Applied Sciences*, 9:1842.
- Kim Y., Wang M., Rhee M.J (2004). A novel alpha-glucosidase inhibitor from pine bark. *Carbohydrate Research*, 339:715–717.
- Liu L.M., Cheng S.F., Shieh P.C., Lee J.C., Chen J.J., Ho C.T., Kuo S.C., Kuo D.H., Huang L.J., Way T.D (2016). The methanol extract of *Euonymus laxiflorus*, *Rubia lanceolata* and *Gardenia jasminoides* inhibits xanthine oxidase and reduce serum uric acid level in rats. *Food and chemical Toxicology*, 70:179-84.
- Loan H.T.P., Bui T.Q., My T.T.A., Hai N.T.T., Quang D.T., Tat P.V., Hiep D.T., Trung N.T., Quy

¹Sở Khoa học và Công nghệ tỉnh Đắk Lắk, Việt Nam;

²Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên, Thành phố Buôn Ma Thuột, Vietnam;

³Trường THPT Phan Bội Châu, Huyện Cu Jut, Tỉnh Đắk Nông;

Tác giả liên hệ: Nguyễn Văn Bón; ĐT: 0842458283; Email: nvbon@ttn.edu.vn.

- P.T., Nhung N.T.A (2020). In-Depth Investigation of a Donor-Acceptor Interaction on the Heavy-Group-14@Group-13-Diyls in transition-metal tetrylone complexes: Structure, bonding, and property. *ACS Omega*, 5:21271–21287.
- Nguyen Q.V., Nguyen N.H., Wang L.W., Nguyen V.B., Nguyen A.D (2017). Free radical scavenging and antidiabetic activities of *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ extract. *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 43:5615–5624.
- Nguyen T.H., Wang S.L., Nguyen A.D., Doan M.D., Tran T.N., Doan C.T., Nguyen V.B (2022). Novel α -Amylase Inhibitor Hemi-Pyocyanin Produced by Microbial Conversion of Chitinous Discards. *Marine Drugs*, 20:283.
- Nguyen V.B., A.D., Kuo Y.H., Wang S.L (2017a). Biosynthesis of α -glucosidase inhibitors by a newly isolated bacterium, *Paenibacillus* sp. TKU042 and its effect on reducing plasma glucose in a mouse model. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 18:700.
- Nguyen V.B., Nguyen A.D., Nguyen Q.V., Wang S.L (2017b). Porcine pancreatic alpha-amylase inhibitors from *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 43:259-269.
- Nguyen V.B., Nguyen Q.V., Nguyen A.D., Wang L.W (2017c). Screening and evaluation of α -glucosidase inhibitors from indigenous medicinal plants in Dak Lak Province, Vietnam. *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 43(6):3599–3612.
- Nguyen V.B., Wang S.L (2018a). New novel α -glucosidase inhibitors produced by microbial conversion. *Process Biochemistry*, 65:228–232.
- Nguyen V.B., Wang S.L., Nguyen A.D., Vo T.P.K.; Zhang L.J.; Nguyen Q.V. Kuo Y.H (2018c). Isolation and identification of novel α -amylase inhibitors from *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. *Research on Chemical Intermediates* 44:1411–1424.
- Nguyen V.B., Wang S.L., Nguyen T.H., Nguyen M.T., Doan C.T., Tran T.N., Lin Z.H., Nguyen Q.V., Kuo Y.H., Nguyen A.D (2018d). Novel Potent Hypoglycemic Compounds from *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. and Their Effect on Reducing Plasma Glucose in an ICR Mouse Model. *Molecules*, 23:1928.
- Nguyen V.B., Wang S.L., Phan T.Q., Pham T.H.T., Huang H.T., Liaw C.C., Nguyen A.D (2023). Screening and Elucidation of Chemical Structures of Novel Mammalian α -Glucosidase Inhibitors Targeting Anti-Diabetes Drug from Herbals Used by E De Ethnic Tribe in Vietnam. *Pharmaceuticals*, 16:756.
- Nguyen V.B., Wang, S.L., Nguyen A.D., Lin Z.H., Doan C.T., Tran T.N., Huang H.T., Kuo Y.H (2018b). Bioactivity-guided purification of novel herbal antioxidant and anti-NO compounds from *Euonymus laxiflorus* Champ. *Molecules*, 24:120.
- Rosenberg B (1962). Electrical conductivity of proteins. *Nature*, 193:364–365.
- Sarukhanyan E., Shanmugam T.A., Dandekar T. (2022). In Silico Studies Reveal Peramivir and Zanamivir as an Optimal Drug Treatment Even If H7N9 Avian Type Influenza Virus Acquires Further Resistance. *Molecules*, 27: 5920.
- Sato K., Nagai N., Yamamoto T., Mitamura K., Taga A (2019). Identification of a Novel Oligosaccharide in Maple Syrup as a Potential Alternative Saccharide for Diabetes Mellitus Patients. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 20: 5041.